

Supplementary Material 2

Supplementary Tables

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Supplementary Table 1. Residual heterozygosity in the founders and F₁ plants of carrot mapping populations L1408×W133 and L1408×W279.

ID	Founder	Homozygous genotype frequency (AA or BB)	Heterozygous genotype frequency (AB)
<i>L1408×W133</i>			
555	L1408	0.76	0.24
070	W133	0.55	0.45
555×070-a	F1-a	0.32	0.68
555×070-b	F1-b	0.37	0.63
<i>L1408×W279</i>			
552	L1408	0.71	0.29
557	L1408	0.44	0.66
398	W279	0.66	0.34
407	W279	0.58	0.42
552×398	F1-a	0.42	0.58
557×407	F1-b	0.38	0.62
407×557	F1-c	0.29	0.71

Supplementary Table 2. Number of markers and maximum spacing for linkage map of chromosomes 3, 8 and 9 of population L1408×W279 constructed using either only homozygous or homozygous + heterozygous. Marker types include homozygous (A×B, B×A), and heterozygous (A×H, H×B, B×H and H×B) markers. A= Homozygous marker for L1408, B= Homozygous marker for W279, and H= Heterozygous marker.

Chromosome	Homozygous		Homozygous and Heterozygous		Number of additional Heterozygous markers	Gap reduction (cM)
	Number of markers	Maximum spacing (cM)	Number of markers	Maximum spacing (cM)		
3	60	19.0	62	13.5	2	5.5
8	15	44.7	24	22.5	9	22.2
9	9	20.4	16	7.8	7	12.6

Supplementary Table 3. Loci significantly associated with root shape traits identified in carrot F_{2:3} mapping populations L1408×W133 (n=119) and L1408×W279 × (n=128). In bold, two QTLs recovered in both populations with an overlapping 1.5 LOD interval (reproducible QTLs).

Trait	Locus	Chr ¹	Map pos ² (cM)	Phys pos ³ (bp)	LOD	%var exp ⁴	1.5 LOD interval ⁵ (bp)	Dom degree ⁶	Allele substitution effects ⁷	
									α	δ
<i>Population L1408×W133</i>										
Shoulder ¹	c.5loc.45	5	45	10886001	6.2	22	7348535-13412756	0.5	-0.7	0.3
Tip ¹	c.3loc.79	3	79	61018994	4.5	16	11742006-61751069	1.0	-0.5	0.5
Biomass	c.8loc.2	8	2	21431131	3.8	14	19453332-32696614	0.2	-343	80
Width	c.3loc.53	3	53	35021817	4.3	16	11742006-63711032	19	0.1	1.9
Width	c.6loc.50	6	50	39847186	4.6	17	14319870-40582356	0.7	1.1	0.8
L/W¹	c.2loc.19	2	19	39653470	5.7	20	32851615-54149218	0.3	-0.9	-0.3
L/W	c.3loc.56	3	56	41614217	4.7	17	11516803-61378990	1.0	-0.6	-0.6
L/W	c.6loc.50	6	50	39875002	4.3	16	14319870-40582356	0.1	-0.7	-0.1
L/W	c.8loc.8	8	0	19453332	5.7	20	19453332-26176663	0.6	-0.8	-0.4
Length	c.6loc.6	6	18	24151730	3.8	14	14319870-29921627	1	-12	12
Length	c.8loc.0	8	0	20539941	7.9	27	19453332-25702759	0.1	-19	-2.4
<i>Population L1408×W279</i>										
Shoulder	c.2loc.18	2	18	44243993	6.1	20	32846084-5070617	0.2	-0.5	-0.1
Width⁸	c.6loc.45	6	45	40259670	5.0	16	37630119-40259670	0.3	1.5	0.5
L/W	c.2loc.34	2	34	53149932	4.3	14	39769213-58630847	0.3	-0.9	-0.3
Length	c.2loc.37	2	37	57786982	3.3	11	39769213-58630847	1	-12	12

¹ Chr=Chromosome, Tip=tip curvature, Shoulder= shoulder curvature. L/W= length-to-width ratio.

² Genetic distances in centimorgans (cM) estimated from linkage maps constructed from F_{2:3} carrot mapping populations L1408×W133 and L1408×W133.

³ Physical position (bp) according to version 3 of the carrot reference genome of the most significant SNP.

⁴ Percent phenotypic variance explained by the QTL estimated as $1 - 10^{-2LOD/n}$ where LOD is LOD score, and n is the number of individuals.

⁵ Support interval for the QTL location in bp.

⁶ Dominance degree, defined as the absolute value of the ratio of dominance to additive substitution effects: $|\frac{\delta}{\alpha}|$.

⁷ α is the additive substitution effect defined as $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}(g_B - g_A)$. δ is the dominance substitution effect defined as $\delta = g_H - \frac{g_B + g_A}{2}$ where g_B and g_A are phenotype means for the two homozygote states and g_H is the phenotype mean for the heterozygote expressed in the units corresponding to each trait.

Supplementary Table 4. List of homologous genes in the OFP-TRM and IQD regulon within 1.5 LOD interval of significant QTLs. In bold are candidate genes 2 Mb or less from predicted genes controlling biological shape.

Trait	SNP ¹ (chrom:pos)	Gene ID	Locus tag	Gene position (bp)	Dist ² (Mb)	Description ³
L/W	SDCARV3_CHR2:39653470	LOC108210025	DCAR_007928	38299380-38300937	1.4	Transcription repressor OFP5
		LOC108206931	DCAR_007743	36783814-36787044	2.9	Domain of unknown function.
	SDCARV3_CHR6:39875002	LOC108208046	DCAR_008585	43315793-43317575	3.7	Uncharacterized (TRM9)
		LOC108224231	DCAR_020875	27642280-27646934	12.2	Predicted protein IQD 1
		LOC108225605	DCAR_020362	32009199-32011469	7.8	Protein IQ-DOMAIN 1-like
		LOC108226575	DCAR_020520	30661816-30664209	9.2	Protein IQ-DOMAIN 14-like
		LOC108226810	DCAR_020721	28906376-28907372	10.9	Transcription repressor OFP6
	SDCARV3_CHR3:41614217	LOC108213599	DCAR_012074	43525575-43526563	1.9	Transcription repressor OFP8
	SDCARV3_CHR8:19453332	LOC108200088	DCAR_027681	20635477-20641073	1.2	Uncharacterized (TRM18)
	SDCARV3_CHR2:53149932	LOC108206091	DCAR_008398	41828348-41832564	11.3	Uncharacterized
LOC108208046		DCAR_008585	43315793-43317575	9.8	Uncharacterized	
Width	SDCARV3_CHR6:39847186	LOC108225605	DCAR_020362	32009199-32011469	7.8	Protein IQ-DOMAIN 1-like
		LOC108225303	DCAR_020324	32328760-32332301	7.8	Protein IQ-DOMAIN 1-like
		LOC108226562	DCAR_020722	22863700-22868859	17	Transcription repressor OFP13
	SDCARV3_CHR3:35021817	LOC108214575	DCAR_011147	33004221-33012820	2.0	Protein IQ-DOMAIN 31-like
		LOC108214737	DCAR_009937	12710628-12715941	22.3	protein IQ-DOMAIN 32-like
		LOC108213599	DCAR_012074	43525575-43526563	8.5	transcription repressor OFP8-like
		LOC108213408	DCAR_012488	47514286-47515260	12.5	transcription repressor OFP12-like
	LOC108211116	DCAR_012508	47684073-47688137	12.6	Protein LONGIFOLIA 1	
Length	SDCARV3_CHR6:40259670	<i>No OFPs, TRMs or IQDs found within the 1.5 LOD support interval</i>				
	SDCARV3_CHR8:20539941	LOC108197110	DCAR_028703	2501780-2507107	4.5	Uncharacterized
		LOC108199732	DCAR_027520	22295708-22300142	1.7	Protein IQ-DOMAIN 14
	LOC108197768	DCAR_027238	24917458-24919729	6.7	Protein IQ-DOMAIN 14-like	

		LOC108200088	DCAR_027681	20635477-20641073	7.1	Uncharacterized
	SDCARV3_CHR2:57786982	LOC108208046	DCAR_008585	43315793-43317575	14.4	Uncharacterized
	SDCARV3_CHR6:24151730	LOC108224231	DCAR_020875	27642280-27646934	3.5	Predicted protein IQD 1
		LOC108226810	DCAR_020721	28906376-28907372	4.8	Transcription repressor OFP6
		LOC108226562	DCAR_020722	22863700-22868859	1.3	Transcription repressor OFP13
		LOC108228003	DCAR_021448	22863700-22868859	1.3	Uncharacterized (TRM22)
		LOC108224245	DCAR_020774	28467273-28472568	4.3	Uncharacterized
Shoulder	SDCARV3_CHR5:10886001	LOC108219819	-	9853096-9855397	1.0	Protein IQ-DOMAIN 14-like
		LOC108221137	DCAR_016221	1326651-1327597	2.4	transcription repressor OFP14
		LOC108220104	DCAR_017186	12549724-12554368	1.7	Uncharacterized (TRM22)
	SDCARV3_CHR2:44243993	LOC108206825	DCAR_007973	38613160-38615754	5.6	Protein IQ-DOMAIN 1-like
		LOC108206589	DCAR_007588	35586356-35589381	8.6	Protein IQ-DOMAIN 14
		LOC108210025	DCAR_007928	38299380-38300937	6.0	transcription repressor OFP5
		LOC108208046	DCAR_008585	43315793-43317575	0.9	Uncharacterized (TRM9)
Tip	SDCARV3_CHR3:61018994	LOC108214575	DCAR_011147	33004221-33012820	28	Protein IQ-DOMAIN 31-like
		LOC108214737	DCAR_009937	12710628-12715941	48.3	protein IQ-DOMAIN 32-like
		LOC108213599	DCAR_012074	43525575-43526563	17.5	Transcription repressor OFP8-like
		LOC108213292	DCAR_010451	23239336-23240569	37.8	transcription repressor OFP8-like
		LOC108213408	DCAR_012488	47514286-47515260	13.5	transcription repressor OFP12-like
		LOC108210824	DCAR_012067	43481190-43485847	17.6	Uncharacterized
		LOC108211116	DCAR_012508	47684073-47688137	13.4	Protein LONGIFOLIA 1
Biomass	SDCARV3_CHR8:21431131	LOC108199732	DCAR_027520	22295708-22300142	0.8	Protein IQ-DOMAIN 14
		LOC108197768	DCAR_027238	24917458-24919729	3.5	protein IQ-DOMAIN 14-like
		LOC108200088	DCAR_027681	20635477-20641073	0.8	Uncharacterized
		LOC108197110	DCAR_028703	2501780-2507107	3.6	Uncharacterized

¹ Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNP) in the column refers to the most significant SNP (highest LOD score) chosen to represent the QTL region. Variants were aligned to version 3 of the reference genome (Coe et al. 2023).

² Physical distance (Mb) between the start of the candidate gene position and the SNP at a significant QTL. Distance is based on the reported physical distance of candidate genes on the assembly GCA_001625215.1, bioproject PRJNA268187.

³ Description. Some candidate genes are labeled as uncharacterized in the NCBI BLAST datasets as they lack functional or predicted annotation. Two TRM conserved motifs were aligned to four previously uncharacterized predicted carrot genes DCAR_008585 (LOC108208046), DCAR_017186 (LOC108220104), DCAR_021448 (LOC108228003) and DCAR_027681 (LOC108200088). All genes are within the 1.5 LOD support interval of QTL peaks controlling length, width and length-to-width ratio in chromosomes 2,5,6 and 8 (See supplementary material 3).